

METHODOLOGY OF CULTIVATING HUMANISTIC QUALITY EDUCATION IN VOCATIONAL COLLEGES

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Abstract

Vocational colleges annually supply a large number of high-quality skilled talents to society. In the context of rapid social and economic development, these institutions have made significant contributions to social progress with their unique characteristics and nature. Gradually, they have entered public view and gained recognition from all sectors of society, creating a favorable situation where they occupy half of higher education, holding a very important position in China's higher education system. Therefore, strengthening humanistic quality education in vocational colleges and cultivating students' humanistic spirit has become an essential prerequisite and foundation for their future development. Based on this, in-depth analysis and research are conducted on methods and strategies for nurturing humanistic spirit in vocational colleges, aiming to better promote their positive development.

Keywords: higher vocational colleges; humanistic quality education

Introduction

In the context of the rapid development of contemporary vocational education, higher vocational colleges, as important grounds for cultivating high-quality technical and skilled talents, not only need to focus on enhancing students' professional abilities but also emphasize the deepening and expansion of humanistic quality education. (Zhong Binglin, 1999) Humanistic quality education is crucial for the all-round development of students, serving as a key link in shaping their values, perfecting their personalities, and cultivating their social adaptability. However, there is a widespread tendency in current higher vocational education to prioritize skills over humanities, leading some students to lack cultural depth, innovative thinking, and professional ethics, making it difficult for them to meet the future society's demand for versatile talents. (He Kekang, 2015)

In this context, exploring the scientific methodology of humanities quality education in higher vocational colleges is of great significance. Methodological research not only needs to take into account the characteristics of vocational education but should also be grounded in the laws of student development. Through multiple pathways such as optimizing the curriculum system, immersing students in campus culture, and empowering practical activities, a distinctive model of humanities quality education for higher vocational colleges can be constructed (Shi Mingyan, 2011). At the same time, driven by digitalization and industrial transformation, methods of humanities quality education must also continuously innovate. They need to both inherit classics and integrate contemporary spirit, ultimately achieving coordinated development between technical skills and humanistic qualities, laying a solid foundation for students' lifelong growth (Hu Lian, 2008).

This paper aims to systematically analyze the practical difficulties of humanistic quality education in higher vocational colleges, put forward feasible princi-

ples, paths and methods of training, and provide theoretical reference and practical reference for higher vocational education to realize the fundamental task of "establishing virtue and cultivating people".

1. The significance of implementing humanistic quality education in higher vocational colleges

Nowadays, with the rapid development of economy and increasingly fierce market competition, there are more and more high requirements for students in higher vocational colleges. Employers not only need employees to master skills and professional knowledge, but also require them to have humanistic quality and good psychological quality.

1.1 The rapid development of higher vocational education highlights the role of humanistic quality education

In recent years, China's economy has been developing at an increasingly rapid pace, requiring more and more talent. The cultural education level of students in higher vocational colleges is generally lower compared to that of undergraduate students. However, most higher vocational colleges prioritize employment as their primary "selling point" to expand their scale, neglecting the cultivation of students' humanistic qualities. As a result, while many higher vocational students possess strong technical skills, they lack a sense of humanistic spirit. Some students engage in littering and verbal abuse, and some even harbor negative psychological tendencies that harm society. Therefore, only by emphasizing humanistic quality education can higher vocational colleges foster well-rounded individuals with comprehensive high-quality attributes.

1.2 The strong demand for talent education in social work

The rapid economic development has intensified market competition, making an already saturated market even tighter. This has made the already challenging job market even more severe. The current employment environment is complex and places high demands on college graduates. Not only do they need professional

skills, but also good moral qualities. A lack of humanities education can lead to difficulties for students in future employment and life. Therefore, to change this situation, it is essential to place greater emphasis on students' humanities education and help them develop comprehensive vocational abilities.

1.3 Humanities education is indispensable in the structure of modern talents

Humanistic quality education can enhance students' humanistic literacy and spirit, strengthen their sense of mission and responsibility, and improve their creativity and innovative awareness. The most fundamental aspect of humanistic quality is cultural literacy. Teachers in vocational colleges cultivate students' cultural literacy through humanistic education, changing the previous emphasis on education over moral education and breaking the bad habit of focusing solely on technical skills while neglecting overall quality. Therefore, strengthening humanistic quality education is crucial.

2. Problems and causes of humanistic quality education in higher vocational colleges

2.1 Problems existing in the humanistic quality education of students in higher vocational colleges

1. Lack of action plan

In the humanistic quality education of higher vocational colleges, the Ministry of Education has provided relatively clear guidelines. However, in terms of implementation from macro to micro levels, higher vocational colleges lack specific recommendations and are insufficiently innovative, leading to a lack of action-oriented planning in the process of humanistic quality education. This is specifically manifested in: no fixed schedule for teaching time planning, and a lack of a sound system in course design.

2. The overall system of the course design

individual level	The group level	social aspect
The concrete expression of aesthetic taste	The paradigm innovation of academic community	The reproduction of cultural space
Poetic reconstruction of lifestyle	Construction of campus cultural symbol system	Ethical turn of public cultural policy
The value consciousness of professional behavior	Living inheritance of intangible cultural heritage	Cultural governance in the digital age

System linkage mechanism: the three forms a spiral upward structure of "knowledge input-value transformation-practice output":

1. Cognitive iteration: Dunhuang mural copying (knowledge) -> reconstruction of artistic aesthetic standards (quality) -> global communication of Digital Dunhuang (form)

2. Value feedback: community poetry festival (form) stimulates people's enthusiasm for reading classics (knowledge), and forms cultural confidence (quality)

This three-dimensional system not only responds to the symptoms of the era of the expansion of instru-

In the humanistic quality education of higher vocational colleges, the content mainly includes the transmission of humanistic knowledge, the cultivation of humanistic literacy, and the shaping of humanistic forms. These three aspects are not only complete processes but also progressive ones. However, at present, most higher vocational colleges only achieve the first stage in educating students' humanistic qualities, while the cultivation of humanistic literacy and the shaping of humanistic forms are either neglected or barely addressed.

The content system of humanistic quality education can be systematically divided into the following three dimensions, which are interrelated and progressive:

(1) Humanities knowledge transmission (cognitive foundation)

Core positioning: to build a framework of humanistic cognition with systematic knowledge, and form cultural memory and ideological coordinates.

Content category: Interdisciplinary knowledge map: general education covering literature, art, history, religion, ethics and other fields

(2) Cultivation of humanistic literacy (value internalization)

Core mission: to transform knowledge into stable value judgment and spiritual character, and build a subjectivity of human personality.

Practice carrier: Academy system and tutor system: the transmission of values through the community of teachers and students

Service learning project: cultivating social responsibility in community oral history collection.

(3) Humanistic form shaping (practical externalization)

The ultimate goal is to transform inner qualities into observable cultural practices and build a benign interaction between individuals and society.

Performance dimension:

mental rationality, but also provides a humanistic solution for the construction of "warm technology civilization".

3. The implementation of humanistic quality education is poor

In some higher vocational colleges, school leaders do not elevate humanistic quality education to a high enough level and pay less attention to it. As a result, humanistic quality education is increasingly neglected in practical teaching, leading to the decline of the status of humanistic quality education in higher vocational colleges.

Figure 2-1 Humanities education

2.2 The reasons for the problems in students' humanistic quality

education in higher vocational colleges:

1. Wrong educational philosophy

In terms of talent training, vocational colleges often have the phenomenon of inaccurate understanding. Vocational colleges should not only cultivate students with certain abilities and relevant practical abilities, but also pay attention to cultivating students' humanistic quality, which also shows that it is essential to carry out relevant humanistic quality education.

2. Lack of educational resources

To successfully promote humanistic quality education, it is essential to have both a positive atmosphere for such education and a team of highly qualified humanistic educators. Most vocational colleges in China were established in the late 1990s. Due to their relatively short history and many having roots as local secondary vocational schools, they lack sufficient cultural

depth and historical accumulation. This makes it difficult to cultivate a team of high-quality humanistic educators, leading to the current shortage of such teachers in vocational colleges.

3. Imperfect education mechanism

Humanistic quality education, as an indispensable part of the educational system in higher vocational colleges, should place humanistic quality education on par with technical professional education. However, in practice, it falls short of expectations. Most school activities revolve around academic affairs, and the cultivation of professional skills is given a more prominent position in the teaching system.

3.Third, ideas and measures to improve the humanistic quality education of college students

3.1 Ideas to improve the humanistic quality education of college students

A survey on the current state of college students' writing skills after entering society shows that 12.3% of all college students have decent writing abilities, while 70.4% are very dissatisfied with their writing skills. A qualified college student not only needs solid

professional knowledge but also strong humanistic qualities, and writing ability is a crucial part of these qualities. It's hard to imagine someone with poor writing skills achieving significant success in future work or scientific research.

3-1 College students' written expression ability questionnaire

The overall poor performance of college students in written expression can be attributed to multiple factors. Primarily, there is insufficient practical training due to the intense pressure of college entrance exams before enrollment. Secondly, it is closely related to the imperfect and unreasonable curriculum design and training models of higher education institutions. How to improve students' humanistic qualities, reform course instruction to better cultivate their innovative and practical abilities, has become one of the key contents of curriculum reform.

1. Reform of Required Courses. First, in response to the common weakness in Chinese language among college students, both "College Chinese" and "Basic Writing" courses are offered in the first year of all majors. Second, to enhance students' cultural literacy and innovation capabilities, elective courses and advanced courses can be added to most major curricula in higher education institutions. Elective courses are designed for students who struggle with learning, aiming to help them achieve success continuously, thereby gradually building their confidence and fostering a positive cycle of learning; Advanced courses not only assist teachers in broadening students' thinking and deepening their understanding but also primarily aim to allow students to showcase their talents and achieve greater improvement. Students have the autonomy to choose between these two types of courses, thus enhancing their choice in required courses and reflecting personalized teaching. Third, by integrating, interweaving, expanding, and adding new knowledge and methods into the textbook content, students can perceive the latest information, which stimulates their innovative awareness and cultivates their innovative spirit.

2. The setup of elective courses. Starting from the actual needs of students, we strengthen the basic content of humanistic quality education: literature, history, philosophy, and art; cultural courses both domestically and internationally. In line with the credit system requirements, students must complete 16 credits of humanistic quality education courses. All students must select 4 credits of art courses and 12 credits of humanities and social sciences courses during their undergraduate studies. In short, the rich variety of elective courses provides a broad space for students to choose teachers and courses.

3. Offer research-based learning courses. Focus on cultivating students' innovative spirit and practical abilities, aiming to develop their character and enhance their adaptability to society. Specific measures include: organizing research activities with different content for various subjects, guiding students in exploratory research to foster their awareness, habits, and attitudes towards scientific research, and teaching them how to conduct research methods.

3.2 Measures to improve the humanistic quality education of college students

1. Continuously explore in teaching design philosophy, emphasizing the cultivation of students' divergent thinking. An important task of teaching design is to bridge the gap between students' book world and real life through the processual, explicit, typical, intuitive, practical, and lifelike nature of teaching content. This facilitates interaction between knowledge and cognition, as well as between individuals and their environment, thereby activating static knowledge and maximizing its effectiveness. Secondly, fully liberate both students and teachers—teachers must design questions and provide guidance with selectivity, openness, and inspiration, addressing issues such as narrow, closed,

and uniform teaching approaches. This provides ample space for students to question, think independently, and imagine freely. Therefore, teachers must prioritize the cultivation of divergent thinking in humanities courses.

Traditional education emphasizes convergent thinking (also known as focused thinking, consensus-seeking thinking, or positive thinking) while neglecting divergent thinking (also known as creative thinking, reverse thinking, or multi-directional thinking). This has deep roots in educational philosophy. The traditional teaching model centers on the teacher, emphasizing one-way knowledge transmission from the teacher to students, treating them as passive recipients of information. The goal is to cultivate students into application-oriented talents who can effectively understand, digest, and apply previous knowledge and experience (but not adept at creating new theories or knowledge). Under this educational philosophy, understanding and assimilating the basic theories and concepts of a subject, as well as comprehending and internalizing what the teacher imparts, becomes the highest requirement and ultimate objective of teaching. Students' ideas and their understanding of all issues must be concentrated and unified within the theoretical framework and fundamental concepts of the discipline. This is precisely the goal that convergent thinking aims to achieve.

Aggregative thinking, due to its requirement that both the content and outcomes of thought be concentrated and unified under traditional concepts or existing ideas, has the advantage of facilitating the transmission of disciplinary knowledge and the mastery of predecessors' knowledge and experience. However, its drawback is that it can easily lead students to believe in textbooks, teachers, and authority, assuming everything in books is classic and everything taught by teachers is truth, without daring to raise any doubts. Therefore, focusing solely on aggregative thinking will keep our understanding at the level of predecessors, making it impossible to generate new theories or new ideas. To innovate, divergent thinking must be emphasized; without divergent thinking, there can be no creative sprout or creative achievement. It can be said that all creation originates from divergent thinking.

2. In the content of instructional design, emphasize key points and focus on cultivating students' innovative spirit and intuitive thinking. Teaching is both a science and an art. Superior teaching skills first manifest in teachers clearly defining the goal of developing students' intelligence: stimulating thought through questioning to promote moderate intellectual activity, fostering the depth, flexibility, and uniqueness of students' thinking. Secondly, teachers should engage all senses—seeing, listening, speaking, moving, and touching—to fully involve students in both hemispheric coordination activities, thereby cultivating their innovative thinking abilities. Thirdly, highlight the importance of guiding students' thinking processes. Teachers should demonstrate their insights based on key and difficult issues, not only helping students understand knowledge but also learning the methods and approaches used in lectures. Teachers should also pay attention to identifying students' moments of insight—timely praising, encouraging, and affirming innovative

ideas and methods—and provide opportunities for self-exploration, self-reflection, and self-creation. This is crucial for developing a scientific learning attitude. Finally, teachers should leave room for imagination, inspiring students to engage in rich and full imagination, enhancing their interest in learning and fostering positive emotions, willpower, and character. In summary, teachers must not only focus on developing students' analytical and reasoning skills but also train them in the thinking patterns needed for innovative activities, using known knowledge to explore unknowns and discover new ideas and rules.

3. Break through the teaching mode of teaching-oriented and establish a new classroom teaching mode

The new classroom teaching mode should inherit and carry forward the advantages of the traditional teaching mode, make up for its shortcomings, reconstruct and design on the basis of the new idea of quality education. It should have the following characteristics:

(1) Establish a multilateral interactive teaching mechanism with students as the main body. The establishment of a new type of classroom teaching model should first consider the status and interrelationships among various elements in the basic teaching process (teachers, students, content). According to traditional educational views, the teaching process consists of two aspects: "teaching" and "learning," with teachers being the main body of "teaching" and students being the main body of "learning." This has established the concept of "dual-subjectivity." However, the perspective of quality-oriented education holds that there is only one purpose of education—comprehensively fostering and enhancing the qualities of those being educated. Therefore, "teaching" and "learning" are inherently integrated, with "teaching" existing because of "learning." After the student's primary position is established, various relationships between teachers and students, among teachers, between teachers and textbooks, between students and textbooks, as well as among students themselves, will sequentially form a network structure. Once this subject-oriented multilateral interactive mechanism is established, it provides more options for teaching practice.

(2) Enhance the diversity and complementarity of teaching methods. The holistic view of quality education dictates that the complexity and variability of the teaching process impose higher demands on classroom instruction. Focusing solely on one type or category of teaching method is no longer sufficient to achieve basic educational goals; it is at least detrimental to the comprehensive development and growth of students' overall qualities. Therefore, we can explore humanistic interactive classroom teaching models primarily based on "cooperative," "communicative," and "discussion" learning methods. Each teaching method has its own strengths and weaknesses, and only through flexible integration and mutual reinforcement can we adapt to new circumstances. We should also increase efforts in inspiration, research, and independent learning, shifting the focus of teaching towards student-centered approaches.

CONCLUSION

In summary, only when students themselves recognize the importance of humanistic spirit can they, under effective external conditions and proper guidance from teachers, truly integrate humanistic spirit with their personal qualities. They can then gain insight into the essence of China's excellent traditional culture, thereby enriching their character and knowledge base.

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